

AFGHANISTAN

TWO DECADES OF MAKING IT WORSE

Understanding Intolerance

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The whole world has seen the failure of health professionals in China and the World Health Organisation of recognising early enough the threat of a serious infection. Hence due to human mental blindness they allowed the infection to cause global chaos and the loss of many lives.

Now we see how the same blindness of Western governments and their military leaders has begun to unleash another deadly threat to the security of all countries with a western style of life. Can they see the threat this poses?

This paper examines the root cause of the blindness and refers to the section on Eurocentricism in other papers - reproduced as Appendix 1 to this paper. Please read this as it is important in getting a true understanding of how current global terrorism has grown in the second half of the 20th century- and with the law of karma working, is at the root of our present problems.

CONTENTS

The basic problem	1	The Law of Karma Behind the Scenes	6
Making the connection	3	The Intolerance of Religious Leaders	7
Intolerance as the cause of terrorism	4	Summary	8
How to reduce the continuance of terrorism	5	Appendix one - Eurocentricism	8

The Basic Problem

This is not a religious document, but a little basic look at religion is necessary so as to understand the root cause of the current global terrorism problem. As far as history records, all civilisations, nations and cultures have developed a system or method of viewing the relationship of human life to what is considered to be its Creator or Benefactor. These systems have arisen to become what has been known as religions. The rules and regulations within such systems seek to regulate the social life of citizens and to turn them from animal selfishness towards being compassionate and beneficial to their fellows; as well as turning their psychology towards the recognition of a Creator (or God). Hence crimes against the society or against individuals are frowned upon and generally punished in some way. This can include misdemeanours or offences considered to be against the religion itself. Most national policing or law systems have their origins in the principles laid down in the scriptures of the various religions that have arisen over thousands of years.

Let's look a little closer at this idea of punishment. If readers have read and understood my paper on "Human Mental Blindness" (HMB) it may become clear that some (or many) individuals, who gain the position of being

in (or taking) control of the religious life of a nation, will have projected onto their religion their personal interpretation of the scriptures, which guide the nature of that religion. This personal projection may be entirely false in relation to their original scriptures, but this false perception will not (and in most cases cannot) be seen by the one who holds the false views. Hence unbalanced focus may occur in the direction of which subjects of human life or behaviour need to be punished, and what that punishment should be. Hence religious leaders, acting on blind illusions, can cause many problems due to their false ideas. Understanding the paper HMB will clarify this as being a highly likely possibility across the globe and at all times. Originally religions are not designed to be violent or repressive. Such behaviour arising through religious leaders, comes from the above illusions based on human mental blindness; directed by their animal instinctive traits.

There is no attempt here to say that any of these systems of religion, with their associated punishments, are wrong or unnecessary in any way. This kind of judgement is for each nation or culture to sort out over time. It is an internal affair of each nation; because the ways and customs of each vary so much one from the other. What is good in one is bad in another; or acceptable in one but not acceptable in another. However, when more than one religion is present inside any country or nation, then the situation for control becomes complex and can become a battle between religions, which may really be a battle between false ideas. This is how it was that the man known as Jesus was tried and executed publically more than two thousand years ago. This came about due to intolerance of the ideas of others. Yet that man who was executed taught tolerance to his followers. So it is clear that it was those who executed him that did not follow any idea of tolerance within their own religion. It is the belief system of those executors which later dominated Europe in a false or mutated form, derived from an ardent protagonist of that religion. All religions mutate, changing their doctrine and giving rise to many sects.

It is this failure to tolerate the legitimate beliefs of others which clearly became one of the hidden founding principles of the nations of Europe who lived under the religion which stemmed from Rome (The Holy Roman Empire). By the term "legitimate" I mean to say - the religion or method of control which any nation has adopted over time. I do not mean by saying "legitimate" that it is acceptable or tolerable to all other nations or other belief systems.

Here we have the root cause of the current waves of terrorism which have caused destruction and loss of life across the globe - intolerance. This is the basic problem.

Making the Connection

Many readers will either misunderstand or not see the connection between the statements made above and the current rise in global terrorism. So let us examine in more detail how we may connect these things. And maybe correct a few misunderstandings.

If the Appendix below on Eurocentricism has been understood, then readers will begin to see how it was that Europeans went all around the world carrying this culture of intolerance of the religions or belief systems of others. This they did for more than five hundred years and to a large list of countries. The French, Italians, British, Spanish and Dutch nations sought to colonise and subdue more than one hundred nations across all five continents of this globe. It was because they had a false concept of their own religion, that they deemed it to be superior to any other belief systems which they encountered in those other countries. At the beginning of their global exploits, all those European countries listed above were dominated by the Holy Roman Empire (HRE). This idea of what their religion should be was largely misguided (i.e. it had mutated) if compared to the actual teaching of the man they claimed to follow. He never would have condoned the kind of intolerance which lead to millions of followers of the same religion being burnt on wooden stakes or otherwise executed. He did not teach violence. The HRE were fully responsible for all those deaths of their fellow citizens; because of their inability to address the psychology of intolerance; and eliminate it.

The HRE was behind the construction of huge buildings (churches, abbeys, cathedrals etc.) Yet the man whose teaching they claim to follow did not recommend going to such places for worship (then called synagogues). Instead he recommended a private personal form of worship in a small room with no others present. The HRE created positions of high importance and authority in its leaders, claiming that their authority came from the Creator Himself. Yet the man whose teaching they claim to follow recommends not seeking to be seen as important in the eyes of others in any way. Instead he recommended his followers to place themselves into the lowest position in society. The current centre of what was the HRE, the Vatican, is one of the richest organisations on this planet; as are many of the other leading sects of that religion in their respective countries. Yet the man they presume to follow recommended giving up all claim to property and wealth. These, and there are many other examples, are what I mean by saying that the HRE's idea of their religion was largely misguided. It had clearly mutated.

Yet all those Europeans, who toured the globe imposing their ideas of religion onto other nations, were completely unaware that they were supplanting the existing belief systems of all those nations with something which

was false. They did not recognise that nations, which may have existed for thousands of years, not only had a "legitimate" form of belief, but also may have had the intelligence to see the falseness in what the Europeans were pushing onto them. Hence their colonisation of other countries carried with it the risk of some people rebelling against the Europeans and their ideas.

In recent times we have seen the recognition that these Europeans were guilty of the above mentioned suppression of the ways of life of other peoples; powered by intolerance. The USA, Canada, the UK, New Zealand, Australia and other nations built from Europeans, have all been exposed as destroyers of the indigenous cultures which they have suppressed all those centuries ago. This was intolerance in the most inhumane way. Hence they are seeking to redress the damage they did over many centuries. Here we may be getting close to making the connection mentioned above.

Intolerance as the Cause of Terrorism

The religion which caused Jesus to be executed had existed for many centuries prior to that time. It then mutated into the false form of the religion which was behind the HRE. A few centuries later it mutated again into another religion which has dominated middle eastern countries. All three of these religions have the scriptures and beliefs of such great men as Abraham and Moses as some of their guiding ideas. All three have different forms of the barbaric idea of blood sacrifice as a way to redemption of the human soul. This is why I use the term mutated above; so as to show that they are not really different beliefs systems, but that they have a common origin. The teachings of the great men who originated their religion are not misguided.

Yet despite the common origin of the above three religions, they have never ceased from fighting each other; arising from their innate intolerance. Especially where one of them has sought to supplant one of the others. They have not always been able to live peacefully side by side. But what they do not realise is that they all have false ideas within the ways they administer their beliefs; and have been responsible for the deaths of many millions of their own fellow citizens within their own system of belief. This arises due to divisions (internal sects of a religion) causing problems arising from the intolerance. So fighting and killing is not only external to the religion but is internal as well. Practice of tolerance would have brought peace to them.

It may be true that the way the people of Afghanistan administered their religion twenty or more years ago, was suppressive to the people of that country. But those nations formed through the ideas of the HRE, are not free from the guilt of doing the same things to their own citizens centuries previously; as well as attempting to destroy other "legitimate" beliefs of the nations they colonised. Are they hypocritical in trying to change Afghan ways? Is not the religious intolerance within Afghanistan an internal

problem of the Afghan people to sort out? The situation may now be worse than it was twenty years ago.

Here I will state that it is the intolerance of Western countries (USA, UK and Europe etc.) of the way Afghans have administered their religion, which twenty years ago has caused the backlash of religious sects operating within Afghanistan to resist Western interference. The same applies to the religious sects within many other middle-eastern countries which, in the last fifty years, have risen up to try and show those Western countries that they should not interfere with the internal and "legitimate" beliefs of other countries. But these westerners apply the idea of human rights violations.

The use of the international human rights list is not appropriate to all countries; because their cultures do not always recognise the coupling of rights and duties. All those human rights come with respective duties; otherwise they are dysfunctional. For example; if I claim the right to live without being harmed by others, it implies I have a duty not to harm others. If I seek to enjoy my possessions such that others will not deprive me of them, then I have the duty not to steal the possessions of others. If I claim to be fairly rewarded through my work in society, it means I should not employ slave or low paid labour. These and many others are examples of how rights and duties are coupled such that one supports the other. If we do not advocate the duties along with the rights, we cannot expect everyone to respect the rights. Yet anyone can find examples of nations or cultures where the recognition of duties is lacking. Within so many countries business people seek wealth from their production of goods in their country (i.e. to be fairly rewarded); but many of these people use slave or very low paid labour within their production methods. The European declaration on human rights has no mention of corresponding duties within it. This shows that even those westerners do not recognise the need to couple rights and duties. If they enforced the need for such duties they could not justify buying goods produced by low paid workers in other countries. Here it shows that the westerners who bang the drum of human rights are guilty of hypocrisy. Also we should see that the list of rights, originally created by western countries, is not appropriate in all cultures; until such times as all corresponding duties are observed. Here again we have the effect of Eurocentricism; western countries imposing their ideas of rights onto others.

How to Reduce the Continuance of Terrorism

Within most of those Westernised nations mentioned above, the populations are allowed religious freedom to practice in any way they wish. This has given rise to many new religious movements (NRMs) many of which are cult like and take over, or brainwash, the lives of their followers. These cults can be very suppressive in the way they control the lives of otherwise free

citizens. Many such NRMs originate from the USA. They send their followers to European countries to knock on the front doors of free citizens to try and recruit new followers. Very few European governments have sought to ban such outsider cults or regulate the way they control their follower's lives. How therefore have the same nations made attempts to interfere with the "legitimate" religions of middle-eastern countries. It is for the people within any country to sort out their own internal false ways which their belief system is being administered. The USA is full of repressive false religious cults. No outside country seeks to interfere with the internal affairs of the USA. It is not the business of other nations or the military side of the way their governments behave, to interfere in the internal ways of another country. On the basis of allowing NRMs in their own countries to control people's lives, it is hypocritical for westerners to interfere with the religious ways of other countries.

It was decades of such interference by the USA and other Western nations which originally gave rise to the terrorism which had bedevilled the USA prior to the UN Trade Centre attack in 2001. How is it that all these Western nations cannot see that it is because they seek to replicate their own way of life within countries where it may be inappropriate? It is this action of theirs which has caused militant factions within those countries to rise up against them.

Many centuries ago Britain was under the domination of the religion imposed by the HRE mentioned above. The British King, Henry VIII, opposed this domination by people from another country over the affairs of his country. He made a serious attempt to eliminate the foreign interference by the HRE. He deposed the leaders of the outside religion, took their wealth and confiscated their land and buildings. How is that different in principle to what those people in Afghanistan wish to do now?

It is because the USA has carried the false idea that it is the policeman of the globe, that they have caused rebellion against their imperial attitude from the middle eastern nations. European countries and the USA are responsible for the rise of terrorism, due to their intolerance. The uprising is only a response of those middle eastern peoples towards others seeking to control their lives. Much like Henry VIII did in Britain.

The Law of Karma Working Behind the Scenes

The only way that such terrorism can be reduced is for all those westernised nations to accept whatever other nations do internally. And to engage with them in a positive way and to become tolerant of their beliefs and the way they administer them. The law of karma states that "you reap what you sow". Our actions will bring back to us a corresponding reaction. This has been shown to be true of the terrorism mentioned here. But it does not mean

the future is fixed and cannot be changed. The other side of "reap what you sow" is that if we enact tolerant behaviour towards other regimes then eventually they will not seek to fight back in the form of terrorism. We can use the law of karma to our benefit by this approach. But first those nations, who believe they are educated, should admit their intolerance and seek to eliminate it from their foreign policies and the way they behave.

The Intolerance of Religious Leaders

This law of karma also applies to the new Afghan leaders who are taking back their country. They need guns and other weapons to suppress the situation in Afghanistan. It is true to say that they would be nothing without those weapons in hand. Such people are really weak human beings. Their only capability is to rule with the law of the gun. They are some of those misguided religious leaders mentioned above; with false views of what their religion should be. Hence if they carry out control of the country with weapons, they can only expect others within the country to oppose them with weapons. You reap what you sow. If they were to throw away their weapons and use political ways to rule the country, they would be opposed by other political ways. This is how such things as democracy arise; giving all the people some say in how the country is governed. But those who rule with the law of the gun, can only expect opposition with the gun. Hence their lives will not be filled with peace and tranquillity. They will ever live with fear and stress. But it is their choice and other countries must allow the law of karma to run its course and not interfere with the affairs of other countries. Incidentally these new religious leaders of Afghanistan say they reject the modern way of life of the West; but those weapons which give them the power to take control come from the modern way of the West. Hypocrisy?

In history all oppressive regimes within countries have eventually failed or been taken over with another oppressive regime. It is only a matter of time. It needs no input from outsiders.

What these Muslim fighters need to realise is that the man they revere so much actually promoted the opposite of what they are advocating. Mohammed went to Medina early on in his life. There he was invited by the religious leaders of more than ten different warring tribes to help them. Their tribes had been fighting and killing each other for more than 100 years and they finally wanted peace more than anything, but did not know how to stop the fighting. These people were Jewish, Arab, Christian and other religious types. There was no Islam then. Mohammed skilfully drafted a document which became known as "The Medina Constitution". He did not ask any of them to give up or change their beliefs or their religion. Instead he showed them a way that they could respect and tolerate each others beliefs. They

accepted his recommendations and the fighting stopped. They learned to live with their different religions side by side. This is the opposite of what the Taliban are promoting. Mohammed was a wise and intelligent man, like Jesus he taught people to live peacefully together and to tolerate each other. If Mohammed went to war it was in self defence only. If I kill a person in self defence the police will not send me to prison or condemn me for it. In the same way we should not misunderstand the actions of a wise and knowledgeable man like Mohammed.

Some of the best friends I have in this world live in the Turkish city of Konya. They are like brothers and sisters to me. When one of them was introducing me to his new wife he said to her, "Alan is not a foreigner, he is family." How wonderful that is! Muslim and Christian, respecting each others beliefs and culture with love and tolerance, living as one family. Why cannot all people live together like that? Tolerance brings love and peace.

Readers need to understand that when I write a paper, its underlying principles are not theory or empty philosophy. The papers are the result of 100% human experience of the best kind. Read my papers with that at the back of your mind and understand that they are true wisdom of humanity.

Summary

To clearly understand what this paper is saying readers will need to work on combining the content of the paper HMB mentioned above and the concepts of both Eurocentricism and karma. This is no mean work and may take a little effort and open mindedness; i.e. being free from preconceived ideas. But it is clear that it is the western countries which seem not able to cease from their centuries old habit of being intolerant of the ways of other cultures; and going into those countries and interfering with the culture and religious way of very different people.

It is when the western countries are honest and admit their habit and their mistake that they will cease to stir up rebellion (hence terrorism) within the religious leaders of other countries.

Appendix One EUROCENTRICISM

So that this paper can be more truly appreciated I wish to introduce readers to a concept which I will call **Eurocentricism**. This is maybe a new word for many, so I need to explain what is meant by it. In my other papers readers will see that, although I was born and educated in England (UK), I have travelled and absorbed the ancient culture of non-European peoples; viz. Pythagorean Sufism and Indian philosophy. This travel to far away countries was not for academic reasons, but for personal interest in the culture of those places visited. Also I went to those places to study under

accomplished masters of the various subjects that I was deeply interested in. Hence in my papers there has been an awakening of this subject of Eurocentricism; meaning that these countries have suffered from impositions which have been introduced or forced onto their culture from European type people and mentioned to me by those masters when teaching me. This information I have dutifully passed on in my other papers.

In my view much of this whole world has become subjected to ideas coming from people who have originated from Europe. So much of the whole world is now suffering from Eurocentricism. These Europeans began their promulgation during times when a fanatic false form of Christianity was gripping them. Hence their fanatic false ideas of their belief system were forced onto other cultures. Later, many of these European countries have given up their fanatic approach to their beliefs; but unfortunately the damage is done, and those other countries, worldwide, are still suffering the effects and have hung on to the fanaticism.

In subsequent centuries this has been followed with the Eurocentric dominance of scientific theories, many of which are also false, in that the unproved theories are taught in schools as if they are fact. Add to this the highly mutable nature of digital ways of living and it now it looks like the world will be ruined due to these things spreading into the lives of all people; taking away their freedom to think and act for themselves in line with their traditional cultures; and giving them weapons and other technology which they never could have produced themselves. Let alone the criminal and other harmful activities through digital means, which they could not have easily derived by themselves.

Yet if we go back to the times when Jesus was living on this planet, Britain was nothing, America was nothing and most of Europe was troubled with barbaric, generally uncivilised, tribes of people beating the brains out of each other, stealing each others valuables and women. These European people, who gradually became more organised and a little more civilised, achieved this due to a few good ideas which were spoken by Jesus. A tiny fraction of his knowledge and philosophy changed a whole continent. Where did Jesus learn to speak in such a way? Few people who have belonged to fanatic religious sects have asked this question. If they had really understood Jesus' teachings they would have dropped their centuries old primitive habit of wanting to make or tell other people (or nations) how to live their lives, now called Eurocentricism.

It is not yet a century since Europeans stopped fighting each other. Yet they have not stopped trying to impose their ideas onto other nations. This imposition is coming from all those types whose ancestry originates in Europe, which ever continent they currently live on. They brought the habit, of telling others what to do, with them to their country and have never stopped it nor have they controlled it; or even realised that it is there. This is what I mean by global Eurocentricism. Europeans do not realise what they have been responsible for.

However, more than two thousand years before Jesus' time there was high civilisation in both China and India. These areas were the centre of the world in terms of technology and knowledge of how to live a noble life. Yet then as now these cultures do not have the habit of telling other cultures how to live their lives. Before Jesus' time middle eastern peoples looked further East for trade, trinkets, teaching and technology. In the city of Taxila (near the modern Afghan - Pakistan border) there was a university which taught all subjects to a high degree. The Harappan civilisation in the Indus valley had architecturally planned cities with organised streets, and drainage systems. They had a sophisticated waste disposal system. Each house had a proper toilet and bathing room. The sewage went through a system of drains getting bigger as they collected the waste to convey it onto agricultural fields for fertilisation. They made building bricks with amazing accuracy and had many technologies relating to pottery, metal smelting, fine jewellery and other manufacturing techniques. All these along with a sophisticated weights and measures system.

All this advancement thousands of years before Europeans and peoples of the Middle East started to become civilised. Other evidence shows that the Harappans of the Indus valley were also living by the ancient knowledge of the Vedas and much of the culture they had then has continued into the present day.¹ Their knowledge and ways have survived thousands of years, without the need to tell anyone that they must also live by it; and much longer lasting than this temporary destructive digital electronic fashion might be.

It was into the area of the Indus valley that Jesus went to find a connection with that ancient teaching. Contrary to the way Eurocentricism has promoted his teaching, it did in fact come from the Indus valley and associated areas. A land where the people of Jesus' time knew to go to get more advanced things which they were not capable of producing. It was where he learned to understand human psychology and how to avoid, or progress beyond, the need to force people or tell them how they must live their lives. Instead he showed the options available and left people to choose the appropriate way for themselves. Hold the above in mind as you read the rest of this paper. It may change your view of the old Eurocentric story told about Jesus, his life and teachings.

And you may consider that old Eurocentric view to now be obsolete.

¹ The Harappan Civilization by Tarini Carr - Archaeology Online